

LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF THE RESIDENTS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT PROGRAMS IN POBLACION 1, MABINI, BOHOL, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the Level of Awareness of the Residents in the Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs in Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol, Philippines in terms of Policy and Plans, Human Resource, Programs and Activities, Structural Resilience, Risk Assessment and Vulnerability, and Disaster Preparedness and Response. 80 residents of Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol in different Puroks were assessed according to their knowledge and awareness level. The researcher used the descriptive survey method of research and use a survey questionnaire to gather the necessary data among respondents of the study. The result of the study on the Level of Awareness of the Residents in the Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs in Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol in terms of Policy and Plans, Human Resource, Programs and Activities, Structural Resilience, Risk Assessment and Vulnerability, and Disaster Preparedness and Response was found to be Aware with a total of 3.07 as the computed mean among all variables.

Keywords: *Disaster Risk Reduction Management, Program, Activities, Residents, Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

In terms of disaster risk, Philippines ranked third among all of the countries with the highest risks worldwide according to the World Risk Report 2018, with index value of 25.14% (World Economic Forum, 2018). Considering the location and geographical context of the Philippines as the risk involving coastal hazards such as typhoons, storm surges, earthquakes and floods. Disaster Risk is the likelihood of loss of life, injury or destruction, and damage from a disaster in a given period (UNDRR Assessment Report, 2015).

Philippines has established risk reduction and management to mitigate the effects of disaster. Under Republic Act 10121, also known as "Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010", which implies "An act strengthening the Philippine disaster risk reduction and management system, providing for the national disaster risk reduction and management framework and institutionalizing the national disaster risk reduction and management plan, appropriating funds therefor and for other purposes". Under this law, it states to "Recognize and strengthen the capacities of LGUs and communities in mitigating and preparing for, responding to, and recovering from the impact of disasters". Increasing public awareness about disaster preparedness is very important (Hargono, 2023).

Talplacido et. al (2022) also reveals in his study entitled "The Level of Disaster Awareness and Preparedness of Families in the Flood-Prone Barangays of San Leonardo, Nueva Ecija" that their level of disaster awareness and preparedness can be fully achieved through acquiring relevant technical activities and programs. Thus, reducing the negative impact of disasters on their families and the community. Exposure to newspapers and television was shown to be substantially associated to the level of disaster risk reduction knowledge (Perez, 2021).

Adhering to this, the NDRRMC forwarded four domains, wherein Barangay LGU of Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol is encouraged to enhance their disaster risk reduction and management activities. These are policy and plans, capability/capacity; emergency preparedness and response; and partner or stakeholder agreement.

Thus, this study outlines the level of awareness of the residents in the implementation of disaster risk reduction and management programs in Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol, Philippines.

Research Questions

The general objective of this study is to determine the Level of Awareness of the residents on the Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs Poblacion 1, Mabini Bohol.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following question:

1. What is the level of awareness of the respondents on disaster risk reduction and management in terms of:
 - 1.1 policy and plans;
 - 1.2 human resource;
 - 1.3 programs and activities;
 - 1.4 structural resilience;
 - 1.5 risk assessment and vulnerability; and
 - 1.6 emergency preparedness and response

METHODOLOGY

The study used a quantitative approach and the research method was descriptive survey method to know the level of awareness of the residents in the implementation of disaster risk reduction and management programs in Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol.

A standardized questionnaire was used in gathering data. The questionnaire presented the profile characteristics and the level of awareness on DRRM of Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol residents in terms of policy and plans, human resource, programs and activities, structural resilience, risk assessment and vulnerability, and emergency preparedness and response.

The sampling process used was stratified random sampling wherein the respondents came from the 5 Puroks of Barangay Poblacion 1 which were Purok Upper Kulo, Purok Lower Kulo, Purok Kamansi, Purok Kaimito and Purok Mangga. The total number of respondents are 80 respondents ranges from 15 years- 60 years old as they were the ones who are fully matured and aware with the barangay activities.

RESULTS

The result of the Policy and Plans shows that the total mean is 3.11 interpreted as Aware. The result of the Human Resource shows that the total mean is 3.06 interpreted as Aware. On the Programs and Activities, the total mean is 3.01 interpreted as Aware. On the Structural Resilience, it shows the total mean is 3.06 interpreted as Aware. On the Risk Assessment and Vulnerability, it shows the total mean is 3.03 interpreted as Aware. And lastly, on the Emergency Preparedness and Response, the total mean is 3.13 interpreted as Aware.

DISCUSSION

On the Level of Awareness of the Residents in the Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs in Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol

According to UNESCO (2010), preparedness plans are dynamic ventures that need to be reviewed, modified, updated, and tested regularly. Active disaster preparedness includes developing comprehensive response plans, monitoring hazards and threats, training emergency personnel, and training members of the communities at risk “to ensure the timely appropriate and effective delivery of relief”.

Table 1. Summary table extent is the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM)

Variables	Mean	Interpretation
Policy and Plans	3.11	Aware
Human Resource	3.06	Aware
Programs and Activities	3.01	Aware
Structural Resilience	3.06	Aware
Risk Assessment and Vulnerability	3.03	Aware
Emergency Preparedness and Response	3.13	Aware
Overall Mean	3.07	Aware

The tables exhibit the level of awareness of the residents in the implementation of disaster risk reduction and management programs in Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol. Interestingly, all variables were interpreted as “Aware” with a computed overall mean of 3.07.

In particular, Emergency Preparedness and Response got the highest mean of 3.13 which is interpreted as “Aware”, followed by Policy and Plans which got a computed mean of 3.11 which is interpreted as “Aware”, meanwhile Programs and Activities got the lowest computed mean of 3.01 and Risk Assessment and Vulnerability with a computed mean of 3.03 but it was interpreted as “Aware”. Additionally, Human Resource and Structural Resilience got an equal computed mean which is 3.06 and both were implemented as “Aware”.

The results of the study conform with the study of Bayugo et. al (2016) that the residents in the Municipality of Rosario, Cavite is aware of the disaster risk reduction management (DRRM) programs of the locality. This means that the LGU ‘s programs related to disaster risk reduction and management are effective.

Moreover, this also aligns with the results of the study of Dignadice (2024) wherein the implementation of disaster risk reduction management (DRRM) programs is highly evident. With that, specific aspects were also found as highly evident such as knowledge building, awareness raising, and etc.

In addition, there is a need to assess and strengthen the awareness of the residents regarding disaster preparedness. Brochures and leaflets may be given to the residents for them to be more oriented and educated of the importance of being prepared during emergencies and disaster occurrences (Maminta, 2015).

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The result of the study on the level of awareness of the residents in the implementation of disaster risk reduction and management programs in terms of Policy and Plans, Human Resource, Programs and Activities, Structural Resilience, Risk Assessment and Vulnerability, and Emergency Preparedness and Response was found to be Aware in all variables among the residents of Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol.

Recommendations

From the findings and conclusion of this study, the following are the recommendations:

The barangay LGU of Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol may continue to implement the Disaster Risk Reduction Activities. The barangay LGU may strengthen the DRRM through various programs for better preparation and protection to natural calamities. The barangay LGU may encourage the residents of Poblacion 1, Mabini, Bohol to be more aware and encouraged to participate in various activities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study has a single author and written in her own words following the ethical standards. The author ensured that informed consent was obtained, participants had the freedom to withdraw at any time, their anonymity was preserved, their well-being was protected, there were no conflicts of interest in conducting the study, plagiarism was rigorously avoided, there was no bias in interpreting the results, and the findings were used solely for research purposes.

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